

Ameliorative Efficacies of Selected Polyphenols on Menadione-Induced Testicular Dysfunction in Wister Rats

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Abstract

Infertility is the most prevalent reproductive problem affecting 10-15% of young couples. Evidences suggest injuries to the testes by reactive oxygen species as a result of drugs. This study investigated the ameliorative effects of selected polyphenols (gallic, betulinic and protocatechuic acids) on menadione-induced testicular dysfunction in rats. Thirty (30) male rats were randomly selected into six groups of five rats each. Group A were fed with normal feed and distilled water, while the remaining were given 10 mg/kg body weight of menadione intraperitoneally for 7 days to induce testicular dysfunction. Thereafter, Group B was given distilled water, while Group C was given 10 mg/kg of addyzoa (reference drug) and Groups D, E, and F were treated with 50 mg/kg of betulinic, gallic and protocatechuic acids respectively for 7 days. Menadione significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) reduced serum concentrations of Follicle stimulating hormone (FSH), Leutenizing hormone (LH), testosterone, testicular cholesterol and sialic acid. The specific activities of superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione transferase, acid phosphatase, alkaline phosphatase and lactate dehydrogenase were all significantly reduced in the untreated group. In contrast, there was a significant rise in malondialdehyde and protein carbonyl concentrations. Whereas, the polyphenolic compounds, significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) increased the serum concentrations of FSH, LH, testosterone, testicular cholesterol and sialic acid levels, with a significant decline in malondialdehyde and protein carbonyl concentrations and a significant rise in the specific activities of antioxidant enzymes. Conclusively, gallic and betulinic acids were more effective than the protocatechuic acid in the reversal of testicular dysfunction induced by menadione.

Keywords: Infertility, Menadione, Oxidative Stress, Polyphenolic a Compounds, Testicular Dysfunction, Testosterone

1.0 Introduction

Infertility is the most prevalent reproductive problem affecting approximately 12.6% to 17% of young couples' population worldwide [1]. Interest in the toxicology of the male reproductive system has received increasing interest in recent years partly because of growing reports of falling sperm counts and increasing reproductive disorders [2]. Documented evidences suggest that injuries to the testes by reactive oxygen species (ROS) play an essential role on sperms motility [3] and the overall male infertility. This can result from

antibiotics and exposure to toxic substances, pesticides, radiations, stress, air pollution, chemotherapy, and inadequate intake of vitamins [4]. Menadione isa synthetic analogue of 1, 4-naphthoquinone with a methyl group at position 3 [5], a pro-vitamin known as vitamin K3 [5]. After intestinal absorption of vitamin K, menadione is generated through catabolism of vitamin K [6]. It appears as an odourless, pale yellow crystalline powder that is freely soluble in toluene but insoluble in water. It is susceptible to light and incompatible with oxidizing substances [6]. It is an over-the-counter nutritional supplement used to

treat symptoms of colitis, hay fever, bleeding, hypoprothrombinaemia, and joint problems [7].

Menadione is being used to treat osteoporosis and prostate cancer in conjunction with vitamin C [8]. Despite these health advantages, there have been reports of negative side effects from improper use which includes haemolytic anaemia, neonatal multi-organ damage, and in a few rare cases, death are some of these accompanying side effects [10]. The US Food and Drug Administration consequently outlawed its usage as supplements in the US [11]. However, it is still administered in several nations due to its low cost.

Phenolic compounds (PCs) are diverse, bioactive and pervasive category of plant secondary metabolites that comprise an essential part of the human diet and are of considerable interest due to their biological properties [12]. During the last few decades, many studies have examined the health benefits of PCs [13]. They are widely used in pharmaceutical experiments to improve the bio-efficacy and bioavailability of conventional drugs. Regular consumption of polyphenol-rich foods may help decrease the incidence of cardiovascular diseases [14], colon cancer, liver disorders, obesity, diabetes, testicular dysfunction etc[15]. In plants, these compounds are commonly synthesized as defence agents against physiological and environmental stimulators[16]. PC's have received more attention in recent years and many aspects of their chemical and biological activities are identified and evaluated. Natural phenolic compounds such as protocatechuic acid, gallic acid, and betulinic acid have been reported by various authors to inhibit testicular and epididymal toxicity associated with various drug uses through different mechanisms of action [17].

Menadione (vitamin K) has been reported by Balogunet al. [31] to cause testicular dysfunction in rats. Meanwhile, the drug has a common over-the counter use by individuals for the treatment of various common ailments and perhaps contributing to the incidence of male dysfunctions observed in men. Due to the availability and the regular and indiscriminate use of this drug, it is of great importance to examine the effect polyphenolic compounds such as protocatechuic acid, gallic acid, and betulinic acid could have on the inhibition of testicular and epididymal toxicity associated with various drugs. Hence, the study aimed to compare the effect of Protocatechuic acid, Gallic acid, and Betulinic acid on Menadione-induced testicular toxicity in male rats.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Menadione and thiobarbituric acid were procured from Sigma-Aldrich Inc (St Louis, MO). Assay kits for cholesterol, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and γ -glutamyltransferase (γ -GT) assay kits were products of Randox Laboratories Ltd (Antrim, UK). Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), and testosterone were products of Monobind Inc (CA). All other reagents used were of analytical grade and supplied by Sigma-Aldrich Inc.

2.2 Experimental Animals

Male Wistar rats (152.20 ± 6.56 g) were purchased from the Animal Holding Unit, Department of Biochemistry, University of Ilorin (Ilorin, Nigeria). They were kept in clean plastic cages, placed in well-ventilated house conditions and supplied with feeds (Capefeed Ltd, Osogbo, Nigeria), and water *ad libitum*. Experimental animals were maintained in accordance with the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals.

2.3 Animal Grouping and Administration

Thirty rats (30) were randomized into six (6) groups of five (5) rats each. Rats in group A (control) were fed basal diet and distilled water throughout the experiment while rats in groups B, C, D, E and F received 10 mg/kg body bw of menadione intraperitoneally for 7 days to induce testicular dysfunction. Group B was left untreated after induction, while rats in Groups C were treated with 10 mg/kg bw. Addyzoa, groups D, E, and F were treated with 50 mg/kg bw. betulinic, gallic and protocatechuic acids for 7 days.

2.4 Biochemical Assays

The activity of superoxide dismutase was determined by the method of Misra and Fridovich [18], catalase activity by the method of Beers and Sizer, [19] while malondialdehyde (MDA) Concentration was quantified according to the method of Ohkawa, et al.,[20], Reduced Glutathione concentration (GSH) [21], Glutathione S-transferase Activity (GST) was determined using the method of Habig et al. [22].

Luteinizing hormone concentration was determined by the method of Morimoto, [23], follicle-stimulating hormone concentration and testosterone concentration was determined by the method described by Tietz, [24], alkaline phosphatase activity and acid phosphatase activity was determined by the method of Wright *et al.* [25], lactate dehydrogenase activity, gamma glutamyltransferase (GGT), serum total cholesterol concentration, sialic acid concentrations and protein carbonyl concentration were determined using the methods described by Weisshaar *et al.* [26], Szasz, [27], Fredrickson *et al.* [28], Shamberger, [29] and Levine *et al.* [30] respectively.

2.5 Data Analysis

Data obtained were expressed as mean \pm SEM of 5 replicates and analysed using one-way

analysis of variance (ANOVA) using graph pad prism 9.0. Data were considered significantly different at $P < 0.05$ (confidence level equals 98%).

3.0 Results

3.1 Concentration of Follicle Stimulating Hormone (FSH)

Menadione significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) reduced the concentration of FSH (1.25 ± 0.13 mIU/mL). Administration of 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa (2.85 ± 0.43 mIU/mL) and 50 mg/kg body weight of betulinic acid (2.75 ± 0.33 mIU/mL) was not significantly different from the control (2.91 ± 0.13 mIU/mL) (Figure 1). However, treatments with 50 mg/kg body weights of gallic and protocatechuic acids had a significant difference in concentration when compared with the control group.

Figure 1: Concentration of follicle stimulating hormone of menadione induced testicular dysfunction treated with betulinic acid, gallic acid and protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.2 Luteinizing Hormone Concentration

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the concentration of the luteinizing hormone ($2.53 \pm$

0.03 mIU/mL). All treatment groups had a significant increase in luteinizing hormone concentration but none of the groups compared well with the control (12.25 ± 0.03 mIU/mL) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Luteinizing Hormone Concentration of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.3 Testosterone Concentration

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the concentration of testosterone in the rats (2.85 ± 0.10 ng/mL). Treatment with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa (10.45 ± 0.18 ng/mL), 50 mg/kg bodyweight betulinic acid (10.35 ± 0.17 ng/mL)

and 50 mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acids (9.96 ± 0.10 ng/mL) had a significant increase in testosterone concentration in the rats while the group treated with gallic acid (11.85 ± 0.90 ng/mL) had no significant difference when compared with the control (12.65 ± 0.11 ng/mL) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Testosterone concentration in menadione-induced testicular dysfunction rats treated with betulinic acid, gallic acid and protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.4 Testes Cholesterol Concentration (TCC)

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the concentration of the testes cholesterol (28.50 ± 0.15 mmol/L). Treatment with 10mg/kg body weight Addyzoa (38.50 ± 1.15 mmol/L) and 50 mg/kg body weight Gallic acid had (88.05 ± 0.65

mmol/L) no significant difference in testicular cholesterol concentration when compared with the control whereas, treatment with 50 mg/kg body weight betulinic acid (36.53 ± 0.35 mmol/L) and protocatechuic acids (35.53 ± 0.15 mmol/L) have a significant increase in testes cholesterol concentrations but did not compare well with the control group (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Testes Cholesterol Concentration of Menadione induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.5 Sialic Acid Concentration

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased the concentration of testosterone in the untreated rats (1.80 ± 0.10 mmol/mg protein). Treatment with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa (4.18 ± 0.12 mmol/mg protein) and 50 mg/kg body weight Betulinic acid (4.20 ± 0.10 mmol/mg protein) had

no significant effect on the sialic acid concentration when compared to the control (3.98 ± 0.15 mmol/mg protein). Treatments with 50 mg/kg body weight Protocatechuic (4.80 ± 0.17 mmol/mg protein) and Gallic acids (3.80 ± 0.10 mmol/mg protein) had a significant increase in sialic acid concentration but did not compare well this the rats in the control group (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Sialic acid Concentration of Menadione induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.6 Specific Activity of Alkaline Phosphatase

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of Alkaline phosphatase ($5.10 \pm$

0.10 UL/mg protein). All Treatments were not significantly different from the control group (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Specific activity of Alkaline phosphatase of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.7 Specific Activity of Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH)

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of LDH (18.95 ± 0.25 u/L/mg protein). Treatment with 10 mg/kg body weight

Addyzoa significantly increased the LDH activity (151.95 ± 1.25 u/L/mg protein) while treatment with 50 mg/kg bwBetulinic acid has no significant difference from the control (118.95 ± 5.25 u/L/mg protein) (Figure 7) and significantly higher than those treated with 50 mg/kg body weights of Gallic and Protochatechuic.

Figure 7: Specific activity of Lactate Dehydrogenase of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.8 Specific Activity of Acid Phosphatase

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of Acid phosphatase. All

Treatments had a significantly increase in the specific activity of acid phosphatase but none compared well with control rats (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Specific activity of Acid phosphatase of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.10 Specific Activity of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD)

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of SOD (0.48 ± 0.10 mmol/min/mg protein). Treatments with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa (0.84 ± 0.18 mmol/min/mg protein), 50 mg/kg body weight Betulinic acid (0.80 ± 0.10 mmol/min/mg protein) and 50 mg/kg

body weight Gallic acid (0.85 ± 0.12 mmol/min/mg protein) were all on the same level of significant differences from the control group. Treatment with 50mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acid (0.76 ± 0.13 mmol/min/mg protein) was not significantly different from the control group (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Specific activity of SOD of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.11 Specific Activity of Catalase

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of Catalase. Treatments with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa, 50mg/kg body weight Gallic acid, and 50 mg/kg body weight

Betulinic acid had no difference in the specific activity of catalase while treatment with 50 mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acid has a significant lowering effect in the specific activity of catalase when compare with the control group (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Specific Activity of Catalase of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.12 Specific Activity of Glutathione s-transferase (GST)

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of GST. Treatments with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa, 50 mg/kg body

weight Gallic acid and 50 mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acid were not significantly different from the control group. Treatment with 50mg/kg body weight Betulinic acid was significantly ($p < 0.05$) different from the control group (Figure 11).

Figure 11: The specific activity of GST of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.13 Specific Activity of Gamma GlutamylTransferase (GGT)

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of GST. Treatments with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa, 50 mg/kg body

weight Gallic acid and 50 mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acid also significantly reduced the specific activity of GGT while Treatment with 50 mg/kg body weight Betulinic acid showed no significant change as it compared well with the control group (Figure 12).

Figure 12: The specific activity of GGT of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.14 Specific Activity of Glutathione peroxidase (Gpx)

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the specific activity of GPx. Treatments with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa and 50 mg/kg body

weight Gallic acid significantly increased GPx activity while at 50 mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acid and 50 mg/kg body weight Betulinic acid there was no significant change as they both compare well with the control group (Figure 13).

Figure 13: The specific activity of GPx of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.15 Malondialdehyde Level

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased the Malondialdehyde level ($13.01 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{mol/mL}$). Treatments with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa, 50 mg/kg body weight Gallic acid ($8.08 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$), and 50 mg/kg body weight Betulinic

acid ($8.68 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$) had no difference on the Malondialdehyde level when compared with that of the control group ($5.78 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$) while treatment with 50 mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acid ($6.78 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$) has a significantly lower concentration of Malondialdehyde when compare with the control group ($7.78 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$) (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Malondialdehyde Concentration of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.16 Protein Carbonyl Concentration

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased the protein carbonyl concentration (5.88 ± 0.25

$\mu\text{mol/mL}$). All treatment groups had no significantly different effect on the protein carbonyl concentration and compared well with the control group (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Protein Carbonyl Concentration of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.17 Reduced Glutathione Level (GSH)

Menadione significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the GSH level ($50.01 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$). Treatments with 10 mg/kg body weight Addyzoa ($81.01 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{mol/mL}$), 50 mg/kg body weight Gallic acid

($80.81 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$), and 50 mg/kg body weight Betulinic acid had no difference from the control group ($80.18 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{mol/mL}$) while treatment with 50 mg/kg body weight protocatechuic acid ($112.27 \pm 1.05 \mu\text{mol/mL}$) has a significantly higher concentration of GSH when compared with the control group (Figure 16).

Figure 16: The Reduced Glutathione level of Menadione-induced testicular dysfunction treated with Betulinnic acid, Gallic acid and Protocatechuic acid.

Note: Each value is a mean of 5 determinations. Bars with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

4.0 Discussion

Menadione is well-documented for its ability to produce reactive oxygen species (ROS), which results in oxidative damage [31]. Interestingly, has also been observed to trigger ROS release in human sperm cells [32]. Cholesterol homeostasis is essential for male reproductive health, as it serves as a precursor for steroid synthesis, which is critical for normal sperm production. Adequate cholesterol levels, maintained through uptake and de novo synthesis, are necessary for optimal testicular function and for steroid hormone synthesis in Leydig cells [33]. In alignment with this study's findings, serum cholesterol levels decreased following a 7-days of menadione induction, while treatments with gallic acid, betulinnic acid, and protocatechuic acid increased cholesterol levels, suggesting adequate cholesterol precursor availability to support spermatogenesis and androgenesis.

LH and FSH are gonadotrophins because they stimulate the gonadal function (the testes in males) [34]. The stimulation enhances the secretion of testosterone and maintenance of normal spermatogenesis [35]. The menadione-mediated decrease in LH could be related to the decrease in testosterone. The increase in these biomolecules suggests that gallic acid, Betulinnic acid and protocatechuic acids promotes spermatogenesis by increasing muscle mass and erectile function in the rats.

Sialic acid on the sperm surface is closely related to sperm maturation and capacitation and sperm-

egg recognition [36], which makes sperm negatively charged to avoid accumulation and covers some antigenic determinants there to increase the survival rate of sperm in the female reproductive tract [37]. It was observed that the sialic acid concentration of the menadione-induced rats was reduced and subsequently increased when treated with natural compounds. This may suggest that these natural compounds could promote the maturation of sperm and hence, help spermatogenesis.

ACP, ALP, GGT, and LDH in the testes offer information about the androgenic nature of the testes. The observed decrease in testicular ALP and ACP in menadione-induced rats may disrupt intracellular and intercellular transport critical for steroidogenesis, spermatogenesis, and cellular development [31]. Treatment with gallic acid, betulinnic acid and protocatechuic acid has shown a positive response to increasing the activities of ALP and ACP which suggests that these natural compounds might have increased intra and intercellular transportation, thereby promoting steroidogenesis, spermatogenesis and differentiation. In early spermatocytes, lactate—rather than glucose—is the preferred substrate for glycolysis. LDH catalyses this reaction in the Sertoli cells, which produces lactate. [38]. Following repeated injections of menadione, the LDH in rats' testicles was reduced, which may have limited the amount of energy available for spermatogenesis. Treatment with the natural compounds enhanced the activity of LDH and GGT and this further confirms the androgenic and

ameliorative effects of these compounds in menadione-induced testicular dysfunction.

Menadionemultiorgan toxicity is linked to a depleted antioxidant defence because of excessive O₂ and H₂O₂ generation [39], hence, this links testicular damage to oxidative stress. CAT and GSH activity seen in this study on induction with menadione is consistent with earlier research by Ibitoye and Ajiboye, [40]. The decrease could have resulted from ROS release [32] leading to overwhelmed antioxidant defence and oxidative attack on cellular macromolecules. Following the induction of menadione, an elevated MDA level was observed in the testes of the rats. This could result in the disruption of membrane structure and loss of function by attacking membrane lipids with oxidative stress [41]. The natural compounds were able to reverse the damages done to the membranes and could be said to have antioxidant properties as they were able to increase the systems defense mechanism against ROS.

The increase in protein carbonyl concentration in the menadione-induced rats suggest that protein was oxidized and this is as a result of the presence of ROS molecules which further confirms the conferment of oxidative stress by menadione. Treatment with the natural compounds was able to ameliorate the protein carbonylation which confirms the antioxidant property of these compounds. The main role of GSTs in any cell type is cell detoxification, i.e., protecting macromolecules from attack by reactive electrophiles, including environmental carcinogens, ROS and chemotherapeutic agents [42]. Sperm seem to use membrane-bound GSTs and extracellular GSH to maintain their motility, viability, mitochondrial status, oocyte-binding capacity, and fertilizing abilities during exposure to H₂O₂ and/or lipid peroxidation products [43]. Moreover, higher levels of GSTM3 have been related to lower cryotolerance in boar sperm suggesting it as a freezability marker of sperm [44]. GPx on the other hand protects the plasma membrane from lipid peroxidation, scavenges superoxide and prevents oxygen formation. In a study consisting of infertile men with unilateral varicocele or genital tract inflammation, glutathione led to a significant improvement in sperm quality [45]. This suggests that the natural compounds confer protective characteristics on the male reproductive system by scavenging and acting as a form of defence against the actions of ROS.

5.0 Conclusion and recommendation

Results from this study revealed that betulinic, gallic and protocatechuic acid are good therapeutically agent for the treatment of testicular dysfunction induced by menadione at an administered dose of 50 mg per Kg body weight. However, further investigated can be done using clinical studies.

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